

Preparation and Characterization of *bis*(alkoxy) *bis*(*p*-biphenyl)-Tin(IV)

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Bis(alkoxy) *bis*(*p*-biphenyl) tin(IV) complexes of the type $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2Sn(OR)_2$ (where R = CH₃, *n*-C₃H₇, *i*-C₃H₇, *n*-C₄H₉, *i*-C₄H₉ or *t*-C₄H₉) have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, ir and ¹H nmr spectroscopy.

CHEMISTRY of metal and organometalalkoxides has been a subject of wide investigations for long time¹⁻⁴. Interest amongst the organotinalkoxides arose with their application as heat stabilizers⁵. Though the number of organotinalkoxides has increased tremendously^{1,2} yet most of them are covered in patent literature and have been characterized inadequately. Present communication deals with the preparation and characterization of some hitherto unknown *bis*(alkoxy)*bis*(*p*-biphenyl)-tin(IV) complexes of the type $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2Sn(OR)_2$ where R = CH₃, *n*-C₃H₇, *i*-C₃H₇, *n*-C₄H₉, *i*-C₄H₉ or *t*-C₄H₉.

Experimental

Well dried and purified reagents such as methanol, *n*-propanol, *i*-propanol, *n*-butanol, *i*-butanol, *t*-butanol and benzene were used. Dichloro *bis*(*p*-biphenyl) tin(IV) was prepared by the redistribution reaction⁶ of tetra(*p*-biphenyl)-tin(IV) and SnCl₄.

Preparation of $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2Sn(OCH_3)_2$: A solution of (0.495 g, 1 mmole) of $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2SnCl_2$ in benzene (~50 cm³) was added dropwise with the help of a dropping funnel to a freshly prepared solution of sodium-methoxide (0.046 g Na, 2 m mole in ~25 cm³ methanol) under anhydrous conditions. The reaction mixture was refluxed for an hour, left overnight to settle sodium chloride and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. White solid $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2Sn(OCH_3)_2$ was obtained in >80% yield. Recrystallization was avoided due to extreme hydrolysable nature of the product. Other alkoxy derivatives were prepared, in more or less similar yield, by the same procedure.

Physical measurements: Ir spectra in the region 4000-250 cm⁻¹ were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model-621 grating spectrometer using KBr pellets. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer at a sweep-width of 900 Hz using TMS as an internal standard.

Results and Discussion

These alkoxy derivatives have been prepared by refluxing the sodium alkoxide with $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2SnCl_2$ in the respective alcohol and benzene.

These complexes are invariably white solids and are soluble in most of the organic solvents such as C₆H₆, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, CCl₄, THF, acetone, alcohol though the solutions become turbid on standing in moist atmosphere. Melting points of the complexes were carried out in an open capillary tube. Physical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSES FOR $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2Sn(OR)_2$ COMPLEXES

Complex R	m.p.	Found (Calcd.) %		
		C	H	Sn
OH ₃	280(d)	64.4	5.3	25.2
		(64.1)	(4.9)	(24.4)
<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	269(d)	66.5	6.3	22.5
		(66.3)	(5.9)	(21.87)
<i>i</i> -C ₃ H ₇	250(d)	66.1	6.2	22.4
		(66.3)	(5.9)	(21.87)
<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	185(d)	67.5	6.7	21.5
		(67.3)	(6.4)	(20.8)
<i>i</i> -C ₄ H ₉	220(d)	67.4	6.5	20.9
		(67.3)	(6.4)	(20.8)
<i>t</i> -C ₄ H ₉	190(d)	67.1	6.5	20.9
		(67.3)	(6.4)	(20.8)

Ir spectra: In the ir spectra of these complexes (Table 2), it is evident that in addition to the presence of characteristic absorption bands due to organic parts (alkyl or aryl), the presence of (C-O) and (Sn-O) stretching vibrations are diagnostically important. Absorption in the region 1060-1030 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to asymmetric and symmetric (C-O) stretching vibrations⁷ which

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TABLE 2—IR BANDS AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS FOR $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{OR})_2$

R	OH_2	$n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7$	$i\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7$	$n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_6$	$i\text{-C}_4\text{H}_6$	$t\text{-C}_4\text{H}_6$	Assignment
3100m,b	3080m,b	3080m,b	3080m,b	3080m,b	3080m,b	3060m,b	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ ring
2850w,b	2900m,b	2900m,b	2900m,b	2920m,b	2920m,b	2900w,b	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ aliphatic
1580m	1580s	1595w	1590s	1585s	1590sh	1590sh	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ asymmetric ring breathing
1480m	1480m	1575m	1480s	1480s,b	1480s	1480s	
		1490s					
1075s	1075s	1075s	1080s	1075s	1070s	1070s	(C-H) in plane deformation
1005s	1000s	1000m	1005s	1005s	1005s	1005s	(C-H) out of plane deformation
825s	820s	810m	810s,b	825sh	820s	820s	
755sh	750s	750s	750s	750s	750s	750s	
687s	690s	690s	690s	695s	690s	690s	
1060m	1055m	1055m	1010m	1025m	965m	965m	$\nu_a(\text{C}-\text{O})$
1030sh	1030m	985m	1025w	970m	950w	950w	$\nu_s(\text{C}-\text{O})$
665m	675m	660m	665s	670m	670m	670m	$\nu_a(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$
615m	605w	600w	615m	615m	610m	610m	$\nu_s(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$
550m,b	550m	545m	550m	550s,b	550s	550s	$\nu_a(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$
490w	490m,b	480m,b	495m	505w	490w	490w	$\nu_s(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$

m=medium, b=broad, w=weak, s=strong, sh=shoulder.

appear below this region in branched chain alkoxy derivatives⁹. Butcher *et al* suggested both (Sn-O) and (Sn-C) stretching vibrations in 700-400 cm^{-1} region. On comparing the spectra with that of $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{SnCl}_2$, absorption at ~ 670 and 615 cm^{-1} has been assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$.

in Table 3. The integrals of different resonances are in accordance with the chemical formulae of these complexes.

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TABLE 3—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFTS IN Hz FOR $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{OR})_2$

Complexes R	$p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$ protons			R Protons		
	d	t	d	OH_2	OH_2	OH
CH_3	-710	-697	-682	-198(s)	—	—
$n\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5$	-714	-666	-657	-55(t)	-380(t)	—
					-148(m)	—
$i\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5$	-691	-662	-650	-178(d)	—	468(m)
$n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$	-704	-678	-652	-65 to	-382(t)	—
				180(m)*	($\alpha\text{-CH}_2$)	—
$i\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$	-689	-675	-662	-74(d)	-306(d)	-112(m)
$t\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$	-720	-684	-670	-108(s)	—	—

* In n -butoxide signals due to $\beta\text{-CH}_2$, $\nu\text{-CH}_2$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ protons appear in the form of unresolvable multiplet.

s=singlet, d=doublet, t=triplet.

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¹H nmr spectra: The ¹H nmr spectra of these alkoxy derivatives exhibit two distinct resonances (i) a complex pattern^{9,10} consisting of a doublet, a triplet and a doublet due to the protons of biphenyl group and (ii) signal or signals due to the protons of alkoxy groups. The ¹H nmr data are indicated